

EFFECT OF SURFACE TREATMENTS ON THE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF BIOCOMPOSITES

Hajime Nakamura, Naoyuki Shikamoto, Asami Nakai, Hiroyuki Hamada
Division of Advanced Fibro Science, Kyoto Institute of Technology /Japan
Matsugasaki, Sakyo-ku, Kyoto 606-8585, Japan
Email m8651028@edu.kit.ac.jp

SUMMARY

Natural fiber reinforced biodegradable resin composites are expected to replace inorganic fiber reinforced thermosetting resin composites. However, interfacial properties between natural fiber and polylactic acid are poor. In this study, the effect of surface treatment on the mechanical properties of natural fiber reinforced biodegradable resin composite by shellac resin was clarified.

Key words: natural fiber, polylactic acid, shellac resin, surface treatment, Micro-braided yarn

INTRODUCTION

Natural fiber reinforced plastics are an interesting alternative to composites based on glass and organic fibers, because natural fibers have the advantages of low density, low cost, and biodegradability. In this circumstance, studies on the natural fiber reinforced have been carried out [1] [2]. However, the natural fiber has also problems as follows;

- (1) Mechanical properties are low.
- (2) Scattering of fiber fineness and strength is wide.
- (3) Impregnation of thermoplastic resin into reinforcement fiber bundle is difficult.

In series of study, the spun yarn was used as reinforcement fiber to solve (1) and (2). Natural fiber is short fiber and has no orientation. It also has wide scattering in fineness, length and strength. Usage of spun yarn is, fortunately, possible to reduce the scattering of the properties by spinning short fiber. Also spun yarn is available for continuous fiber which can be used for textile processing. Moreover, Micro-braided yarn was employed as an intermediate material for high impregnated continuous fiber reinforced plastics, in

which traditional Japanese braiding technique was applied, to solve (3). Micro-braided yarn is fabricated by braiding resin fibers alongside reinforcement fiber. Since resin fibers are located close to reinforcement fiber bundle, impregnation performance is excellent [3].

The interfacial adhesion between reinforcement and matrix is very important for mechanical properties of composites materials. A weaker interface reduces the efficiency of stress transfer from the matrix to the fiber and consequently the strength and stiffness are not high. However, the interfacial properties between natural fibers and aliphatic polyesters such as polylactic acid are inadequate, because natural fiber contains numerous hydroxyl groups that are strongly hydrophilic [4]. Thus, surface treatment of natural fiber for improved adhesion is a critical step in the development of such composites. Before now, the treatment as dewaxing (defatting), acetylation, chemical grafting, and silane coupling were used for modifying the surface properties of the fibers [5] [6] [7] [8].

In this study, shellac resin was used for surface treatment to improve the interfacial properties between Jute fiber and polylactic acid. Shellac resin is one of the thermosetting resins of animal origin secreted by the lac insect. Shellac resin has been used as coating materials in various fields such as industrial materials, medicines, and food ingredients due to various unique properties such as thermoplasticity, oil resistibility, cohesiveness, insulating ability and nonpoisonous nature. Thus, by using shellac resin, all-biobased composites could be fabricated. Fig. 1 shows the chemical structures of the main compositions of shellac resin. They contain polar functional groups such as hydroxyl group [9]. Because Jute fiber also contains polar functional groups, it is expected to improve interfacial properties by using shellac resin.

In this paper, by using shellac resin treated Jute spun yarn / PLA Micro braided yarns unidirectional specimen was fabricated. The effect of surface treatments on the mechanical properties of Jute spun yarn / PLA composites was investigated.

Fig. 1 Main compositions of shellac resin

MATERIALS AND TESTING METHOD

Materials

Jute spun yarn (170 tex) was used as reinforcement fiber. As a resin fiber, Polylactic acid (PLA) fiber (Lactron, 16.7 tex, Kanebo synthetic fiber), naturally-derived biodegradable thermoplastic resin fiber, was used. As surface treatment, shellac resin (Gifu Shellac Ltd., Japan) was used.

Shellac resin treatment

The Jute spun yarn was treated with aqueous solution of shellac resin (Gifu Shellac Ltd., Japan). Next, the shellac resin treated Jute spun yarn was dried at 80 °C for 2h. The concentration of shellac resin was varied (2.0wt%, 3.0wt%, 4.0wt%, 5.0wt%, 10 wt%).

Composites processing: fabrication of the unidirectional composites

By using treated Jute spun yarn as axial and PLA resin fiber as braiding yarn, Jute/PLA Micro-braided yarn was fabricated by tubular braiding machine. The Micro-braided yarn was wound unidirectional around a metallic frame. Then, the Micro-braided yarn was placed in a heated die and molded to produce unidirectional test specimen by the optimum molding condition (in molding pressure of 1.33MPa, molding temperature of 190°C, molding time of 8 min).

3-point bending test was performed by using INSTRON universal testing machine (model 4206). The specimen size was 50 mm in length, 15 mm in width. The span length was 25 mm and the test speed was 1mm/min.

Tensile test was performed by using INSTRON universal testing machine (model 4206). The specimen size was 200 in length, 20 mm in width. The span length was 100 mm and the crosshead speed was 1 mm /min. At the same time, strain was measured by strain gage (gage length 10 mm).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Evaluation of the interfacial properties

First, the effect of surface treatments on interfacial properties was investigated by

using bending test in 90 degree direction. Since fracture on interface between fiber and matrix occurred, bending test in 90 degree direction was applied to clarify the interfacial properties. Relationship between bending properties in 90 degree direction and concentration of aqueous solution of shellac resin is shown in Fig. 2. The bending modulus was decreased by shellac resin treatment. By contrast, the bending strength was increased until 4.0wt% and decreased over 5.0 wt%.

The results of cross sectional observation of specimens in 90 degree direction are shown in Fig. 3. Despite concentration of shellac resin, the unimpregnation region couldn't be seen. However, there was difference in dispersion of Jute fiber bundle. In the case of untreated and 2 wt%, the fiber bundle areas were almost same. By contrast, in case of 5.0 wt%, the fiber bundle area was 90% of other concentrations, namely, dispersion of the Jute fiber couldn't be seen.

The results of the cross sectional observation of specimens after bending test are shown in Fig. 4. In the case of untreated, the fracture occurred in the interface around fiber bundle. In the case of 4wt%, the fracture occurred in the interface inside fiber bundle. However, in the case of 10wt%, the fracture occurred in the interface around fiber bundle as much as untreated.

Next, to investigate quantitatively the interfacial properties, the following evaluation method was applied. The typical stress-deflection curve of 90 degree bending test is shown in Fig. 5. There is an initial fracture point. Since the initial fracture occurred in the interface between filament and matrix resin, in this research the initial fracture stress was considered as interfacial strength. Moreover, the stress-deflection curve was divided into 3 regions and calculated the energy absorption of the each region ; energy absorption until initial fracture point, energy absorption from initial fracture point to maximum stress point and energy absorption after max stress point.

Relationship between the initial fracture stress and concentration of shellac resin is shown in Fig. 6. The initial fracture stress was increased until 4.0wt% and decreased over 5.0 wt%. Relationship between the each energy absorptions and concentration of shellac resin is shown in Fig. 7. The energy until initial fracture point was increased until 4.0wt% and decreased over 5.0 wt%. Moreover, the energy from initial fracture to max stress point was increased largely until 4.0wt%. By contrast, the energy after max stress point was constant despite concentration of shellac resin. In the region from initial fracture point to max stress point, onset and propagation of crack had been observed so in this research the energy could be regarded as "crack propagation energy".

Observation of fracture surface was performed by using SEM to investigate the condition of the interfacial adhesion of resin on Jute fiber. The SEM photographs of fracture surface of specimens are shown in Fig. 8 (a) ~ (d). In the case of untreated, adhesion of the resin on the Jute fiber couldn't be seen. In the case of 4.0 wt%, adhesion of the resin on fiber was observed. Moreover, resin was elongated and ductile fracture occurred compared to untreated.

From these results, interfacial strength and crack propagation energy were increased until 4.0 wt% by increasing in interfacial adhesion. However, apparent interfacial strength and crack propagation energy were decreased over 5.0 wt% without dispersion of the Jute fibers since Jute fiber bundles were binded with shellac resin, and impregnation of PLA resin into fiber bundle was difficult.

Fig. 2 Relationship between bending properties in 90 degree direction and concentration of shellac resin

Fig. 3 Cross sectional observation of specimens

Fig. 4 Cross sectional observation of specimens after bending test
a) untreated, b) Shellac 4wt%, c) Shellac 10wt%

Fig. 5 Stress-deflection curve

Fig.6 Relationship between initial fracture stress and concentration of shellac resin

Fig. 7 Relationship energy and concentration of shellac resin

Fig. 8 SEM photographs of fracture surface of specimens (a) untreated, surface treated with (b) shellac 2wt%, (c) shellac 4wt%, (d) shellac 10wt%

Evaluation of the mechanical properties

The effect of surface treatment on the tensile properties was investigated by tensile test. The thickness of specimen was changed by concentration of various concentration of shellac resin and as a consequence the fiber volume content (V_f) was varied. Thus, the achievement ratio was used to compare the tensile properties of specimens with various surface treatments. Achievement ratio was calculated by normalizing the experimental value with theoretical value. The theoretical value was calculated by rule of mixture.

Relationship between tensile properties of the specimen and concentration of aqueous solution of shellac resin is shown in Fig. 9. Achievement ratio of elastic modulus was constant despite concentration of shellac resin. By contrast, the achievement ratio of tensile strength was increased until 4 wt% and decreased over 5 wt%.

Observation of fracture surface was performed by using SEM to investigate the condition of the interface of the specimen. SEM photographs of fracture surface after tensile test are shown in Fig. 10. In the case of untreated, space between Jute fiber and matrix resin was observed and adhesion of the resin on the Jute fiber couldn't be seen. In the case of the shellac 4wt%, the space wasn't observed and adhesion of resin on fiber was observed.

From these results, tensile properties were improved until 4.0 wt% by increasing in interfacial strength and resistance of crack propagation. And tensile properties of 5.0 wt% became low without dispersion of Jute fiber bundle.

Fig. 9 Relationship between achievement ratios of tensile properties and concentration of shellac resin

Fig. 10 SEM photographs of fracture surface after tensile test

CONCLUSION

In this study, the effect of surface treatment on the mechanical properties of natural fiber reinforced biodegradable resin composite by shellac resin was investigated. The interfacial strength between jute fiber and PLA resin and resistance of crack propagation were improved by shellac resin. Consequently, by shellac treatment, mechanical properties were increased until 4wt%. But, dispersion of Jute fiber bundle was interrupted over 5wt% and the mechanical properties were decreased.

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